

Studies on Human Serum Esterase using Substituted Phenyl Acetates as Substrates

R. L. NATH* and H. DEBNATH

Biochemistry Department, School of Tropical Medicine, Calcutta-12

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Human serum esterase was utilised to hydrolyse phenyl, *m*-methylphenyl, *p*-methylphenyl and *p*-chlorophenyl acetates at the optimum pH determining kinetically for each the Michaelis constant, K_m whose reciprocal, the affinity constant K_a showed on correlation with Hammett's substituent constants, that the enzyme-substrate complex formation is facilitated by electron attracting substituents. Inhibition studies indicated the participation of a divalent metal and non-participation of any ϵ -amino group of lysine or any thiol group from the enzyme molecule. The mechanism for complex formation postulates the metal bound to the enzyme with two valencies and to the two oxygen atoms of the substrate with two other valencies. The breakdown of the complex is considered to be by an attack of a hydroxyl ion of the medium upon the acyl carbon whose fission with the bridge oxygen ultimately produced phenol, acetic acid and free enzyme.

THE influence of electron displacement by a substituent in the benzene ring, upon a reaction at the side chain, has been explained in many organic reactions in terms of Hammett's equation^{1,2} in which a constant, σ (designated substituent constant), as determined by Hammett¹, is attributed to each substituent to measure its electron displacement power along the ring. The idea has also been extended to enzymatic reactions for arriving at the mechanism of action in case of β -D-glucosidase³, acid phosphatase^{4,5}, alkaline phosphatase^{5,6} etc. Although esterase can hydrolyse substrates with substituted benzene ring, this approach to determine its mechanism of action has not been reported in the literature. It was, therefore, decided to study this enzyme from human serum using some substituted phenyl acetates as substrates and thereby, to arrive at a mechanism of action.

Experimental and Results

Preparation of substrates :

Phenyl acetate, *m*-methylphenyl, *p*-methylphenyl and *p*-chlorophenyl acetates used as substrates were prepared after Vogel⁷, the finally purified products having the same B.P. as given in the literature.

Preparation of active enzyme :

Pooled human serum was estimated for its esterase activity per g. of protein against phenyl acetate by the method described below, the protein content being determined by the Biuret method⁸. Serum proteins were then precipitated with five volumes of cold acetone, settled for 2 to 3 hr., centrifuged, washed

three times with cold acetone and dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid for 72 hr., all work being done below 15°. The esterase activity per g. of this acetone powder increased 2.2 times over that in serum, similar preparation with ethanol giving an increase of 2 times only. The acetone powder was used in the present work.

Method of hydrolysis :

Experiments for the enzymatic hydrolysis of an ester to produce acetic acid and corresponding phenol were started by adding the enzyme solution using a stop watch, to a preheated emulsion previously prepared by mechanically stirring a mixture of desired quantities of a substrate, phosphate buffer at appropriate pH (after Green and Hughes⁹), water, bile salt solution and gum acacia solution, the last two maintaining the final over-all concentrations of 0.03% and 0.3% respectively; 5 ml. samples of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at appropriate time and placed in 5 ml. of distilled water already kept in a boiling water bath, thereby stopping the enzyme action. The acetic acid produced by hydrolysis was estimated by titrating the cooled sample with 0.04N NaOH against phenolphthalein and the difference of titres of the samples at zero min. and after a fixed interval gave the degree of hydrolysis during that interval expressed in molar concentration of acetic acid which was obtained from calibrations previously prepared by titrating equimolecular mixtures of acetic acid and corresponding phenol in different concentrations. The detailed conditions of hydrolytic experiments are mentioned in respective tables.

One unit of esterase activity was represented by 1 ml. of 0.04N acetic acid liberated under the experimental conditions.

* Present Address : Head, Biochemistry Department, R. K. Mission Seva Pratisthan, 99, Sarat Bose Road, Cal.-26.

Determination of optimum pH :

Hydrolytic experiments were performed at different pH withdrawing samples at zero min. and 30 min. and the acetic acid formed during this interval represented the activity at respective pH. The optimal for all the four substrates was pH 7.4.

Determination of the order of the over-all reaction :

The molar concentration, X of the substrate decomposed during any interval (i.e., the molar concentration of acetic acid formed) was subtracted from the initial molar concentration of the substrate (S_0). The decadic logarithm of $(S_0 - X)$ plotted against time gave a straight line providing the first order and the corresponding velocity constant, k_0 was obtained from the slope of this straight line as usual. The results for the experiment with *p*-chlorophenyl acetate are shown in Table 1 and Fig. 1. Others are omitted for brevity.

TABLE 1—FIRST ORDER OVER-ALL REACTION OF ESTERASE AGAINST *p*-CHLOROPHENYL ACETATE

Buffer, 0.05M phosphate; pH 7.4; Temperature, 37°; Titre, 0.04N NaOH; S_0 , initial molar conc. of substrate; t , time in min.; k_0 , first order velocity constant; 0.5 ml. of enzyme solution (30 mg./ml.) was used with 24.5 ml. of buffer-substrate emulsion; X , molar conc. of substrate decomposed.

t	Test titre ml.	Activity titre. ml.	X	$S_0 - X$	$\log (S_0 - X)$	k_0
0	1.85	—	—	0.0200	-1.6990	
10	2.42	0.57	0.0040	0.0160	-1.7959	
20	2.75	0.90	0.0064	0.0136	-1.8655	
30	3.01	1.16	0.0086	0.0114	-1.9431	0.0185

Fig. 1. First order over-all reaction of esterase against *p*-chlorophenyl acetate.

Determination of the Michaelis constant, K_m and Affinity constant, K_a :

Hydrolytic experiments were performed with three different concentrations of the substrate calculating $1/k_0$ in each case. The plot of $1/k_0$ against

S_0 , the initial molar concentration of the substrate gave a straight line whose intercept on the X-axis was equal to the negative value of the Michaelis constant, K_m as shown by Veibel¹⁰ and Pigman and Goepf Jr.¹¹. The reciprocal of K_m gives the Affinity constant, K_a . The results for phenyl acetate are presented in Table 2 and Fig. 2 omitting others for brevity. Table 3 shows K_m and K_a values for all the substrates together with the σ -values for the corresponding substituents, taken from Hammett's book¹. Fig. 3 shows the correlation of $\log K_a$ against σ -values.

Fig. 2. Determination of K_m for esterase against phenyl acetate.

Inhibition studies :

Inhibition study on serum esterase using EDTA (disodium salt), iodine and *o*-methyl isourea was carried out to detect respectively the participation of a divalent metal¹², a thiol group¹³, and an ϵ -amino group of lysine^{14,15}, of the enzyme molecule in the complex formation with the substrate.

Fig. 3. Correlation of σ -values with K_a -values.

(a) *Inhibition by EDTA* : Hydrolytic experiments using phenyl acetate were performed with and without the addition of EDTA analysing 5 ml. samples of reaction mixture at zero min. and 30 min.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF THE MICHAELIS CONSTANT, K_m FOR ESTERASE AGAINST PHENYL ACETATE

1 ml. of enzyme solution, 30 mg/ml, was used with 24 ml. of buffer-substrate emulsion; other conditions as in Table 1

S_0	t	Test titre ml	Activity titre ml	$X \cdot 10^3$	$S_0 - X$	$\log(S_0 - X)$	$1/k_0$
0.04	0	2.14	—	—	0.0400	-1.3979	
	4	2.99	0.85	6.5	0.0335	-1.4750	
	8	3.60	1.46	11.1	0.0289	-1.5391	
	12	4.16	2.02	15.2	0.0248	-1.6055	25.3
0.05	0	2.25	—	—	0.0500	-1.3010	
	4	3.15	0.90	6.9	0.0431	-1.3655	
	8	3.78	1.53	11.6	0.0384	-1.4157	
	12	4.38	2.13	16.1	0.0339	-1.4698	31.2
0.06	0	2.30	—	—	0.0600	-1.2218	
	4	3.29	0.99	7.5	0.0525	-1.2798	
	8	4.05	1.75	13.2	0.0468	-1.3298	
	12	4.58	2.28	17.2	0.0428	-1.3686	35.4

K_m from Fig. 2 0.01

TABLE 3—RATE CONSTANTS AND σ -VALUES OF SUBSTITUENTS OF THE SUBSTRATES USED

Substituent	K_m -value	K_a -value	$\log_{10} K_a$	σ -value
H	0.010	100.0	2.000	0.000
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	0.034	29.4	1.468	-0.069
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	0.015	66.6	1.823	-0.170
<i>p</i> -Cl	0.004	250.0	2.398	+0.227

(b) *Inhibition by iodine*: Ice cold enzyme solution was diluted to twice the volume with water and adequate 2 mM solution of iodine so that the concentration of iodine in the mixture was 250 μ M. This iodine-enzyme mixture, cooled at 5° for 30 min was used for the hydrolytic experiment as with EDTA keeping an over-all iodine concentration, 50 μ M. The experiment was repeated with different concentrations of iodine using two different substrates e.g., phenyl acetate and *p*-chlorophenyl acetate. The results are shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4—RESULTS OF INHIBITION STUDIES ON ESTERASE

3 ml. of inhibitor treated enzyme solution was used with 12 ml. of buffer-substrate emulsion. Other conditions as in Table 1.

Substrate with initial conc.	Inhibitor with conc.	Zero min. titre, ml.	30 min. titre, ml.	Activity titre, ml.	$X \cdot 10^4$	Degree of hydrolysis in per cent
Phenyl acetate 0.05M	None	3.12	7.00	3.88	294	58.8
	EDTA, 0.002M	3.30	3.92	0.62	47	9.4
	Iodine, 50 μ M	3.20	7.06	3.86	294	58.8
	„ 100 μ M	3.17	7.05	3.88	294	58.8
	„ 150 μ M	3.10	6.98	3.88	294	58.8
	„ 200 μ M	3.15	7.03	3.88	294	58.8
	<i>O</i> -methyl isourea, 14.5mM	3.40	7.26	3.86	294	58.8
	„ 29.0mM	3.40	7.26	3.86	294	58.8
<i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl acetate 0.05M	None	2.25	4.65	2.40	157	31.4
	Iodine, 50 μ M	2.35	4.76	2.41	157	31.4
	„ 100 μ M	2.30	4.70	2.40	157	31.4

N.B. There is no inhibition except with EDTA. The degree of hydrolysis being 58.8% without and 9.4% with EDTA, the inhibition due to the latter is 49.4% of the hydrolysis.

The enzyme solution was incubated for 15 min. with equal volume of EDTA solution (20.0 mM) at room temperature and then used. For the experiment without EDTA the enzyme solution was treated similarly with equal volume of water. The results are given in Table 4.

(c) *Inhibition by o-methyl isourea*: *O*-methyl isourea solution (145 mM) was prepared in the cold by dissolving 0.1 g. of its sulphate, CH₃OC(NH)NH₂·H₂SO₄ (m.p. 118°-20°; M.W. 172.16; made by Ralph N. Emanuel Ltd., Wembley, England) in 0.1 ml. of water, adding 3.9 ml. of a saturated solution

of $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ to precipitate the sulphate, removing excess of $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ by CO_2 and then filtering and adjusting the pH to 7.4 with phosphoric acid. The enzyme solution was incubated with equal volume of *o*-methyl isourea solution¹⁵ for 1 hr. at 5° and the experiment carried out as with EDTA repeating with a different concentration of the inhibitor. Table 4 shows the results.

Fig. 4. Mechanism of action of esterase upon substituted phenylacetates.

Discussion

The present study with partially purified human serum esterase hydrolysing phenyl, *m*-methylphenyl, *p*-methylphenyl and *p*-chlorophenyl acetates gave an optimum pH of 7.4 for this enzyme against each substrate almost agreeing with the optimum pH of 7.5 for other mammalian esterases¹⁶. But it differed from plant esterases which have optimum pH in the acid range¹⁷.

In the enzymatic reaction, $E + S \xrightleftharpoons[k_2]{k_1} ES \xrightarrow{k_3} \text{Products} + E$

Products + E, the Michaelis constant $K_m = \frac{k_2 + k_3}{k_1}$

but k_3 is negligibly small in comparison with k_1 or k_2 and hence it equals k_2/k_1 ,¹⁶ the equilibrium constant for the dissociation of the enzyme-substrate complex. When the over-all reaction is of the first order the K_m may be determined by Veibel's method¹⁰. This has been utilised in the present case; Fig. 1 showing first order k_0 and Fig. 2 giving the K_m determination.

The correlation of $\log K_a$ with Hammett's σ -values (Fig. 3) proved the facilitation of the complex formation by electron attraction by substituents represented in Fig. 4 which gives the proposed mechanism. This electron attraction by substituents causes an electron deficiency in the carbonyl carbon which is further enhanced by the shift of electrons in the double bond of this group. The electron-rich and electron-poor centres in the substrate thus created are attached to the oppositely charged centres in suitable positions of the enzyme molecule. Besides the carbonyl oxygen, the bridge oxygen also has free electrons for binding. The significant inhibition by EDTA (Table 4) proved the presence of a divalent metal in the reactive site, of the enzyme. The thiol group appears to be absent since iodine has no inhibition which agrees with previous finding on

esterases from other sources¹⁸. The presence of ϵ -amino group of lysine in the respective site also could not be established due to the lack of inhibition of *o*-methyl isourea^{14,15}. The mechanism of complex formation represented in Fig. 4 postulates the attachment of the enzyme to two oxygen atoms of the substrate through a divalent metal, M having a co-ordination number 4 and fixed to the enzyme molecule at two unidentified electron donating points \ddot{X} and \ddot{Y} in it.

The complex is considered to be hydrolysed by an attack of hydroxyl ion of the medium on the carbonyl carbon breaking the acyl oxygen bond with the consequent reversal of the electron shift along the double bond and removal of the electropositivity of this carbon. The link between the metal and the carbonyl oxygen is also broken forming free acetic acid. The next step removes the attachment of the metal with the phenolic oxygen which receives a hydrogen ion from the medium to form free phenol. The alternative possibility of the attack of the hydroxyl ion upon the phenolic carbon of the bridge is ruled out because of its lesser electron deficiency compared to that of the carbonyl carbon.

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